

Experimental evaluation of hybrid inter-module joints Performance of steel modular buildings under lateral loading

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a series of three cyclic tests have been carried out on meso-scale joint prototypes in order to investigate the in-plane structural response of steel modular buildings that employ a novel type of hybrid inter-module connection. The newly developed inter-module connection has a hybrid configuration, comprising custom steel corner fittings, a high-damping rubber bearing and a high-strength steel bolt assembly and has been designed to improve the demountability and reusability of steel modular buildings subjected to lateral loading. A previous proof-of-concept finite element analysis study has revealed the working mechanism of the connection and the contribution of each part at component level. The current stage has been to conduct experimental tests by adopting the FEMA-SAC standard protocol on a bi-axial loading configuration to determine the mechanical behaviour of the connection at joint level. The tests have showcased the favourable cyclic performance of the hybrid inter-module joints, supported by the connection's demountability in the aftermath of the cyclic load protocol, the presence of a self-centring effect, and the limited permanent damage in the connection's components.

Keywords: steel modular buildings, inter-module connections, high-damping rubber, cyclic loading

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel Modular Building Systems (MBSs) have emerged as a compelling modern method of construction (MMC) due to the attractive prospects of pre-engineered, ready-made volumetric modules (1; 2). The trend of building taller self-standing steel MBSs has drawn the attention of researchers toward the crucial role that inter-module connections (IMCs) play in the stability and resilience of modular structural systems subjected to lateral loading such as earthquakes (3; 4).

Out of the plethora of IMCs in the literature, the authors have conducted a comprehensive review (5), highlighting the paucity of connections designed to participate effectively to the lateral behaviour of modular buildings without relying on the damage-inducing hysteresis of the steel framing members. Given the large number of connection points in a typical multi-storey steel modular building, there is a lot of potential in harnessing a more pronounced contribution of inter-module connections to the global damage distribution mechanism of such structures.

To bridge the gap between the limited disassembly and reuse opportunities of steel modular buildings caused by the lack of structural resilience and underperforming connections, the authors have introduced a novel hybrid IMC, developed to improve the re-centring capacity of the inter-module joints as well as limit the plastic deformations that occur in the main framing members. The mechanical behaviour of the proposed connection has first been revealed through a proof-of-concept FEA study that predicted the contribution of each connection part under the main deformation modes, showcasing a favourable cyclic performance at component level (6).

The present paper focuses on the next stage of the investigation, that of carrying out a series of cyclic loading tests designed to study the in-plane structural response of hybrid inter-module joints

subjected to lateral loading in order to understand the force-transfer mechanism at joint level and reveal the re-centring capabilities of the hybrid connection.

2 THE NOVEL HYBRID INTER-MODULE CONNECTION

The assembly illustrated in *Fig. 1* depicts a corner IMJ assembled with a laminated elastomeric bearing (LEB) as a core clamped between the steel box corner fittings of volumetric modules by means of a bolt assembly. The size of the box corners was restricted to that of the connecting frame members with a flush finish to allow members to be closely fitted together at external or internal IMCs where more than two modules are connected, without increasing the horizontal gaps between modules which would act adversely to the stiffness of the structure.

The connection has been designed to fulfil the essential functions of vertical and horizontal connectivity between modules, while the centred alignment of the member cross-sections to the box corners eliminates the unfavourable effect of eccentric loads caused by offsets. Axial compression is transferred between the corner posts through the laminated elastomeric bearing made with steel reinforcing plates to control the level of vertical displacement, whereas tensile axial force is resisted by the bolt assembly. Horizontal shear forces are transferred through a combined mechanism of friction between the faying steel surfaces and the superposition of shear resistances of the rubber layers and bolt rod, while the interlocking pins prevent accidental sliding.

Fig. 1. Illustrated representation of the hybrid inter-module connection

3 INTER-MODULE JOINT TESTS

3.1 Details of test joints

The test IMJ prototypes were made of top and bottom beam-column subassemblages, and the inter-module connection between them, corresponding to the meso-scale configuration depicted in *Fig. 2*. This solution was preferred for its cost-effectiveness, as it replicates the deformed shape and anticipated points of inflection in planar modular frames subjected to in-plane lateral loads by limiting the lengths of the posts and beams to half of those in the full-size frame panel.

Fig. 2. Schematic of meso-scale IMJ prototypes

The tests focused on the influence of six parameters on the mechanical behaviour of the hybrid IMJ prototypes as summarised in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Test parameters

Test joint no.	Bolt assembly	Beam-column joint
TJ01	M24, class 8.8 bolt	Unstiffened
TJ02	M24, class 8.8 bolt	Stiffened
TJ03	M27, class 8.8 bolt	Stiffened

3.2 Details of test connection components

Top and bottom beam-column subassemblages of S355J2H steel grade were made from standard cold-formed hollow members welded to box corner fittings as shown in *Fig. 3*. The stiffened prototypes in tests TJ02 and TJ03 had two 100 mm x 100 mm x 10 mm triangular plates welded at the beam-column intra-connection, aligned to the outer walls of the hollow profiles.

The high-damping rubber bearing (*Fig. 4*) was made of two outer steel plates (150 mm x 150 mm x 15 mm), four rubber layers (150 mm x 150 mm x 4 mm) and three steel shims (150 mm x 150 mm x 3 mm), designed to achieve a shape factor of $S = 8.85$ to improve the stability of the bearing and limit the bulging of the rubber layers.

The bolt assemblies shown in *Fig. 5* used in the tests included standard M24 x 150mm and M27 x 100mm full-thread hexagon head bolts of class 8.8 high-strength steel.

Fig. 3. a) beam-column subassemblies, b) box corner fittings (units: millimetres)

Fig. 4. Layout of the rubber bearings (units: millimetres).

a)

b)

Fig. 5. a) M24 bolt, b) M27 bolt

3.3 Loading system and instrumentation details

The test rig illustrated in *Fig. 6* has been designed to accommodate the bi-axial loading applied to the top column of the IMJ prototypes. This loading system has been chosen for its ability to realistically replicate the deformed shape of unbraced modular frames subjected to a lateral load, including the contribution of the connecting framing members and the effect of the beam-column joint (7).

The loading program begins with the application of 100 kN axial load over the time span of one minute, which is kept constant in the subsequent cyclic load stage. The axial load magnitude corresponds to 5% of the compressive yield capacity of the column's cross-section, $N_{c,Rd}$, as defined in Eurocode 3, Part 1 (8) for members not susceptible to local buckling failure and exerts a compressive stress of 4.7 MPa on the rubber bearing.

The test followed the prequalification and cyclic qualification testing provisions as per ANSI/AISC 341-22 (9), applying the displacement-controlled standard FEMA/SAC (10) loading sequence given in Table 2, through the horizontal actuators in a quasi-static manner at a rate of 10mm/min to limit the influence of dynamic effects such as those arising from the inertial forces of the joint prototype members.

Details of the transducer layout for the vertical and horizontal displacement measurements can be seen in *Fig. 7*.

Fig. 6. Test frame and details of loading system

Fig. 7. Transducer layout

Table 2. Cyclic loading protocol

Load step	Storey drift angle, θ	Equivalent lateral displacement	Number of cycles
1	0.375%	10.3 mm	6
2	0.5%	13.8 mm	6
3	0.75%	20.6 mm	6
4	1%	27.5 mm	4
5	1.5%	41.3 mm	2
6	2%	55 mm	2
7	3%	82.5 mm	2
8	4%	110 mm	2

4 TEST RESULTS

4.1 Load-displacement curves

The hysteretic curves of the test prototypes have been plotted in *Fig. 8* using the total force and average displacement values recorded by the two horizontal actuators used to apply the cyclic lateral load. The load-displacement curves present valuable qualitative indications of the stiffness, strength, as well as recoverable displacement of the hybrid connection, thus reflecting its mechanical behaviour at joint level.

As shown in *Fig. 8*, all three test prototypes have reached the end of the cyclic loading protocol, completing two cycles at $\theta = 4\%$ storey drift angle, meeting both the strength degradation ($\theta_{SD} = 2\%$) and ultimate ($\theta_U = 3\%$) minimum qualifying capacity criteria for ordinary moment frame systems, as well as the minimum qualifying capacity criterium at strength degradation ($\theta_{SD} = 4\%$) for special moment frame systems, as defined by FEMA/SAC guidance (10).

The shape of the load-displacement curves is highly representative of the typical S-shaped hysteretic curve of high-damping rubber under shear loading, characterised by a brief zone of high initial stiffness that quickly turns into a plateau, followed by an abrupt stiffening as the shear strains in the rubber reach larger levels. This is particularly evident during the small amplitude cycles ($\theta = 0.375\% - 0.5\%$) in which the main contribution is provided by the rubber bearing, while the bolt hole tolerance allows the sliding of the bolt assembly without providing much resistance. Once the storey drift angle reaches $\theta = 0.75\%$, the bolt assembly becomes locked under the shearing action between the top and bottom box corner fitting plates, contributing to the lateral stiffness of the joint

through a combined shear bending deformation state which is marked by the stiffness increase seen on the load-displacement curves.

Overall, it has been observed that the negative loading direction (pulling) registered a slightly stiffer response for all test prototypes, owing to the presence of the ceiling and floor beams on the right hand side of the joints. Hence, the unsymmetrical configuration of the joint prototypes was also reflected in the unsymmetrical load-displacement curves.

The two bolt sizes as well as the two details of beam-column joints have exposed further differences in the behaviour of the three test prototypes, highlighting the influence of each parameter on the structural response of the hybrid inter-module joints. The presence of stiffener plates at the beam-column joint has proven critical for the completion of the cyclic load protocol without loss of strength or stiffness, as demonstrated by the behaviour of prototypes TJ02 and TJ03, in contrast with prototype TJ01 which exhibited weld crack failure at the peak of the first $\theta = +4\%$, followed by a peak lateral load reduction of about 15% during the reverse loading cycle. Increasing the size of the bolt from M24 to M27 was marked by an improvement in the stiffness and lateral load capacity seen in the behaviour of TJ03, specifically in the positive loading direction of the $\theta = 4\%$ cycles.

In terms of residual lateral displacement, it was found that the stiffened beam-column joints in TJ02 and TJ03 had a favourable effect on the re-centring capability of the joints, improving the recoverable displacement.

Fig. 8. Load-displacement curves

4.2 Self-centring capacity and demountability

In order to further quantify the re-centring capability of the test prototypes, the self-centring capacity of each joint has been determined as the percentage of recoverable displacement (i.e., the difference between the peak lateral displacement reached in a cycle and the residual displacement registered during the reverse loading direction). The self-centring capacity curves have been displayed in Fig. 9.

The curves revealed a rapid surge in the self-centring capacity of the three test prototypes during the small amplitude storey drift cycles between 0.375% and about 1% - 1.5%. At the same time, it was found that all joints had overall better self-centring capacity in the negative loading direction up to a storey drift angle of $\theta = 3\%$, which can be explained again by the contribution of the beams acting favourably on the right hand side of the test prototypes. However, once the storey drift angle of $\theta = 4\%$ was reached, the difference between the two loading directions has been reduced in all hybrid inter-module joints, both sides exhibiting self-centring capacities of approximately 70%.

The use of stiffened beam-column joints (TJ02 and TJ03) and larger size bolt assembly (TJ03) enhanced the maximum self-centring capacity reached during the 2-3% storey drift cycles, while also moderating the decline exhibited by joint prototype TJ01 during the $\theta = 4\%$ cycles.

To support the demountability claims of the hybrid inter-module connection, all joint prototypes have been disassembled with ease at the end of the test programme. The connection components

have been taken out and examined as illustrated in *Fig. 10*, to check the damage state in the rubber bearings and the bolt assemblies.

As shown in *Fig. 10 a)*, all rubber bearings displayed signs of residual shear deformation, owing to the breakage of the bonds between the carbon black filler and the chain network particles within the high-damping rubber layers as well as due to strain crystallisation to a certain extent during the large amplitude cycles in which the rubber layers are subjected to shear strain percentages of up to 100%. In spite of these results, no signs of delamination of rubber layer rupture have been noticed, confirming the good manufacturing quality of the bearings. Overall, the most pronounced residual deformation has been observed in the rubber bearing from test TJ01, suggesting that the unstiffened beam-column joint resulted in more demanding force transfer mechanisms from the bearing.

In spite of the deformed shapes of the bolt assemblies illustrated in *Fig. 10 b)*, none of the bolts were jammed at the end of the cyclic load protocol, allowing for easy unfastening using a regular spanner. As expected, the effect of stiffened beam-column joints was seen to increase the deformation when the same size of M24 bolt assembly was used in tests TJ01 and TJ02, while this effect was reduced when a larger size M27 bolt was adopted in test TJ03.

Fig. 9. Self-centring capacity curves

a)

b)

Fig. 10. a) Residual shear deformation in the rubber bearings, b) Bending deformation of the bolts

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper has showcased the mechanical behaviour of a novel hybrid inter-module connection through a series of three meso-scale cyclic loading tests, including the effects of test parameters such as bolt size and detail of the beam-column joints. The findings revealed the favourable effect of the stiffened beam-column joints and larger size bolt assembly on the stiffness and strength properties of the test prototypes, while also supporting the connection's demountability in the aftermath of the cyclic load protocol, the presence of a self-centring effect, and the limited permanent damage in the connection's components. Further work on the development of simple design formulae and the development of macro-mechanical joint models for adoption in global analysis studies is actively carried out by the authors and will be the subject of follow-up research on the novel hybrid inter-module connection.

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